

The Dies Natalis of Iulia Augusta Numidica Simitthensium and of Augusta Treverorum

A. C. Sparavigna

Polytechnic University of Turin - Department of Applied Science and Technology

Here we propose literature about the Dies Natalis of the Roman colony Iulia Augusta Numidica Simitthensium, that is Simitthus, today Chemtou, Tunisia. The Dies Natalis of the colony, founded by Augustus, was on November 27th. Moreover, we will show how literature, in particular Panegyrics, are giving us the Dies Natalis of Augusta Treverorum, today Trier. The Dies Natalis was on July 25th. This date clearly shows that there is no connection of the Dies Natalis with any supposed alignment of the decumanus, the main street of the town, with sunrise.

Keywords: Roman colonies, Tunisia, Germany, Dies Natalis

Torino, February 23, 2024

In Eckstein, 1979, we can find a study about the Dies Natalis of the Roman colonies. Eckstein explains that the Romans traditionally commemorated a definite day of the year, and that this day was celebrated as the Dies Natalis, the "birthday" of the colony (see also Sparavigna, 2020). "The question to be considered is: what action in the long sequence of actions necessary for the legal and practical founding of a colony did such a "birthday" commemorate and celebrate?" (Eckstein, 1979). The ancient Latin literature does not provide a definition of this day. We discussed in detail the different proposals about the birthday of roman towns in Sparavigna, 2022.

Eckstein says that we know this day just in the case of four colonies. They are: "Saticula: 1 January (Festus, p. 358 Lindsay); Brundisium: 5 August (Cic. Pro Sest. 131; cf. Ad Att. 4.14); Placentia: in all probability, 31 May (Ascon. In Pis. p. 3 Clark, with Madvig's emendation; cf. now A. M. Eckstein, "Two Notes on the Chronology of the Outbreak of the Second Punic War," forthcoming in RhM); Bononia: 28 December (Livy 37.57.7)" (Eckstein, 1979).

Here we show that we can add to this short list two cases: Iulia Augusta Numidica Simitthensium and Augusta Treverorum. Let us stress that the dates of these two cases are based on ancient literature and epigraphy. They have nothing to do with archaeoastronomy, as we will show specifically in the case of Augusta Treverorum. Sometimes, it happens to find dates regarding the foundation of ancient towns, which are proposed on the basis of the alignment of their main street along the sunrise direction, for instance [Alexandria of Egypt](#); these proposals are questionable. They are coming from an old theory proposed by Heinrich Nissen, in his *Das Templum*, 1869, theory that had been criticized with strong evidences by Isaac Valeton and C. O. Thulin in the past and recently by Pierangelo Catalano and many others (see [The Town and the Templum](#)).

Simitthus

Simitthus in Tunisia hosted a roman colony created by Augustus. We can find information in J. Linderski, "Natalis Patavii", 1983. "It is well known that not only homines and dei, but also collegia, templa and urbs had their dies natalis. First of all we have the natalis of Rome on April 21, the feast of Parilia When in 57 BC Cicero was coming home from his exile he landed on 5 August in Brundisium: ibi mihi Tulliola mea fuit praesto natali suo ipso die, qui casu idem natalis erat et Brundisinae coloniae et tuae vicine Salutis (Att. 4,1,4). In a later period, in 185 AD an inscription from Simitthus in Africa Proconsularis records the natalis civitatis, no doubt of

Simitthus. In the fourth century we hear that Constantine celebrated the natalis of Trier, but above all we should not forget the birthday of the New Rome, the genetia of Constantinople on 11 May. And finally an entry in the lexicon of Souda contains information about the feast of Astydromia which was celebrated para Libusin to commemorate tes poleis genetia, presumably of Cyrene.”

In Linderski’s notes we can find details about Simitthus: “CIL VIII 14683 a = ILS 6824, a decree of the curia Iovis. The prescript reads as follows: curia Iovis. acta /V k. December / Materno et [A]ttico cos. / natale civi[t]atis. J. Schmidt, Statut einer Municipalcurie in Africa, RhM 45, 1890, 599-611, eps. 606, 610, points out that the Concilium of the curiales took place on 27 November, the anniversary of the foundation of the colonia (natale is here an abl. = natali). Simitthus was established as a colony by Augustus, see F. Vittinghoff, Römische Kolonisation und Bürgerrechtspolitik unter Caesar und Augustus, Abh. Mainza 1951, Heft 14, 112 n.2.

As it is evident, there was a colony of Augustus founded on November 27th. Some told that no colonies were founded in November, because it was an inauspicious month, that is, a month of bad omens. History says otherwise. Today, there are persons who claim to know more than Augustus did about the colonial foundation.

Fig.1: Chemtou in Google Maps

Fig.2: Map Courtesy it-ch.topographic-map.com.

In the Google Maps we can see that Simitthus had a Roman marble quarry.

An article by Philipp von Rummel and Dennis Mario Beck tells us that Simitthus/Chimtou, is the city of the "numidian marble". <https://www.dainst.blog/tana/simitthus-chimtou-2/>

“Ancient Simitthus (modern Chimtou, Tunisia) is located in northwestern Tunisia near the Algerian border. ... the city was part of the former Roman province Africa Proconsularis for over 500 years. The site is most famous for its important quarries of yellow Numidian marble. ... The site Simitthus, however, has much more to offer than the quarries and the mentioned excavated areas. As a major Roman town, it has several temples, three public squares, baths, nymphaea, a theatre, an amphitheater, an aqueduct of 14 km length, and a labor-camp for the imperial administration, prisoners, and workmen. Furthermore, it is one of only few North African cities that witnessed a settlement ranging from the Iron Age to the Middle Ages. ... Simitthus became part of the Roman province Africa Nova in 46 BCE and was granted the status of a colony under Augustus named Colonia Iulia Augusta Numidica Simitthensium. After almost 500 years of Roman rule, the region became part of the Vandal Kingdom in 439 CE.” (Rummel & Beck).

In The Oxford Classical Dictionary, 2012, R. J. A. Wilson, we can find told that Chemtou is at the crossroads of the major routes from Carthage to Hippo Regius and Thabraca to Sicca Veneria. The importance of the site, however, is coming from the quarries of yellow fine marble, mentioned by Pliny too. This marble was used by Numidians who built a temple (possibly in memory of Masinissa). “Simitthus marble was first imported in Rome in 78 BC (Plin. HN. 36,49), and then on a greatly increased scale from Augustus onwards, who used it in his own forum (forum Augusti) and for the colonnade of Caesar’s forum (forum Caesaris) (Suet. Div. iul. 85). ... Augustus founded a colonia at the site, and it continued to flourish into the 3rd cent. at least; ... A unique discovery near the quarries is a 3rd cent. ergastulum for the quarry workers, converted in the 3rd cent. into a workshop for fashioning plates, basins, and statuettes of giallo antico for the export market” (Wilson, 2012).

Trier

We have found information about colonia Iulia Augusta Numidica Simitthensium, Dies Natalis November 27, in Lindersky. As we have reported, Lindersky is also mentioning Trier.

It seems that Augusta Treverorum was founded by Augustus during his stay in Gaul in the year 16 B.C., near a military settlement that seems to date back to about 30 B.C. The exact date cannot be established by the historical sources of the time, but by a series of circumstances that occurred in those decades (this is the information about the foundation that is proposed by [Wikipedia](#)). However, we do know something about Trier Dies Natalis. In Eckstein it is told “In the fourth century we hear that Constantine celebrated the natalis of Trier”. In a note: “Paneg. Lat. 6 (7), 22,4 Mynors: *video hanc fortunatissimam civitatem, cuius natalis dies tua pietate celebratur.*” It is a panegyric of Constantine, available [digiliblt](#) .

C. E. V. Nixon, in “The occasion and date of Panegyric VIII(V), and the celebration of Constantine's Quinquennalia”, tells “In this paper I [Nixon] argue that Panegyric VIII(V) was delivered on 25 July 311, at the completion of the celebration of Constantine’s Quinquennalia.” In fact, on July 25, 306, Constantius Chlorus died near Eburacum, today York. His army, led by the Germanic general Crocus, proclaimed Constantine the new Augustus of the West ([Wikipedia](#), Epitome de Caesaribus, 41, 3).

The date July 25 is coming from “Constantine's thirtieth anniversary celebration (tricennalia) at

Constantinople, at which Eusebius recites his *In Praise of Constantine* (25 July)” (Bardill, 2012). July 25 was the Constantine’s *dies Natalis Imperii*. And also: “Proclaimed Augustus on 25 July 306 by his father's troops” (Barnes, 1982). “Constantine himself regarded 25 July 306 as his sole *dies imperii* from at least 310 (Pan. Lat. 6(7).9.2; Lactantius, *Mort. Pers.* 25.5), and there is no need to postulate an official *dies imperii* later than 25 July 306 in order to explain the attested examples of his imperial titulature. That hypothesis ... carries the corollary that at some date Constantine regarded himself as not yet an emperor in the intervening period—which is both improbable in itself and contradicted by the panegyric of 307: “cum tibi pater imperium reliquisset, Caesaris tamen appellatione contentus expectare malueris ut idem te qui ilium declararet Augustum” (Pan. Lat. 7(6).5.3)” (Barnes, 1982).

Fig.3 - Aula Palatina, Konstantinbasilika in German, at Trier, Germany. This Roman palace basilica was built between AD 300 and 310 during the reigns of Constantius Chlorus and Constantine the Great (Kleiner, 2014). Photo courtesy Pudelek (Marcin Szala). Map courtesy Google Maps.

Let's go back to Nixon. The panegyric was read on the occasion of the Trier *dies natalis*. Trier was “the only city with any plausible claim to Constantine’s continuous presence in this period”.

In De Beer, 2004, it is explained that C.E.V. Nixon had a “counting” of panegyrics which “differs from the Bude series, edited by Galletier, in which Panegyric V is VIII and Panegyric VI is VII. The reason for this is that Galletier orders them chronologically, whereas they came down to us in the opposite order. The panegyrics of Constantine are: “Panegyric VII/6 del 307 – Panegyric VI/7 del 310 – Panegyric V/8 del 311 – Panegyric XII/9 del 313 – Panegyric IV/10 del 321” (Marconi, 2013).

In Marconi, 2013, we find detailed information on Panegyric VI/7 of 310. It is told that the speech was given on the beginning of celebrations for quinquennalia of the Constantine’s reign (at the beginning of the fifth year), on July 25, 310; on the day of the anniversary of Trier foundation, the panegyrist, aware of his limitations, proposes to celebrate Constantine alone. The first part of the text is dedicated to the military victories of emperor's father, Constantius Chlorus. The second part of his eulogy recalls the conspiracy of Maximian and the clash with Constantine, which culminates in the battle of Marseilles and the usurper’s death, spared by Constantine but not by gods. On the way to the Rhine, Constantine stops at the temple of Apollo near Autun, and there the god predicts eternal glory to him. The panegyrist, therefore, invites the emperor to return to Autun and encourage its recovery and, thanking him, recommends his children and pupils to him, ... and so on (Marconi, 2013).

As for Panegyric V/8 of 311, the text was recited on 25 July 311 on the end of celebrations for the Constantine’s quinquennalia, in Trier, by an anonymous orator from Autun. The panegyrist starts

telling that he feels himself compelled to explain why the speech of thanks, for the benefits granted to Autun by the emperor, is being given in Trier. Hence it is proposed the explanation of why Autun deserved imperial benefices. First the Aedui, called brothers of the Roman people, favored Julius Caesar in the conquest of Gaul, and then in more recent times, ... and so on (Marconi, 2013).

So, from ancient literature, we know that the Dies Natalis of Trier was July 25th.

An archaeoastronomical theory exists regarding the foundation of Roman colonies/cities that says that their decumanus is oriented with sunrise on the day of foundation. This is an old theory proposed by Heinrich Nissen, in his *Das Templum*, 1869. We discussed in [SSRN](#) and in “[The Town and the Templum](#)”.

It is enough to look at any map of Trier to see that both decumanus and cardo have no orientation at sunrise on July 25th. Therefore, the Dies Natalis of Trier, July 25th, does NOT correspond to a date of sunrise aligned with decumanus (or cardo).

Fig.4 - Trier as shown by the website <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com> which we thank for the tool it makes available for study and research.

If we look at the topographic map, it's hard to think that the nature of the place didn't influence the orientation of the town.

An archaeoastronomical date of Trier has been proposed by Espinosa et al., 2016.

Here's what Espinosa et al. say, in the abstract of their work: “The aim of the present paper is to extend the archaeoastronomical study sample on the orientation of Roman cities to the analysis of a number of cases in the Rhine area. The starting point is a study of the orientation of Augusta Treverorum (present day Trier; Goethert, 2003). Goethert assumed that the orientation of the decumanus maximus was towards sunrise at the autumn equinox, on September 23rd as the dies natalis of the city. This event would deliberately coincide with the anniversary of the birth of Augustus, and would have determined the establishment and orientation of the new urban layout. However, our in situ measurements of the orientation of the urban network at several sites of the Roman town rule out this hypothesis. ...”. In the text by Espinosa et al. we find that: “As regards the urban layout of Augusta Treverorum, the decumanus maximus and the forum are oriented towards sunrise on the first days of March and mid-October. ... Here we (Espinosa et al.) propose that these dates are related to the “war season”, ritually defined in Roman traditions and perhaps also in Celtic culture ... Therefore, the choice of these dates in the case of Augusta Treverorum does not seem arbitrary, and could have been motivated by the desire of the Roman authorities to signal the start and end of the “war season” and, according to this, the “government of Mars” in the civic life of the Treveri.”

This is not the case, because the DIES NATALIS of TRIER was on JULY 25th. There is no connection with the season of war. There is no reason to say that the government of Mars influenced Trier. The Trier Dies Natalis was 25 July, as told by literature!

References

- Bardill, J. (2012). *Constantine, Divine Emperor of the Christian Golden Age*. Cambridge University Press. ISBN:9780521764230, 0521764238
- Barnes, T. D. (1982). *The new empire of Diocletian and Constantine*. Harvard University Press.
- Catalano, P., & Haase, W. (1978). Aspetti spaziali del sistema giuridico-religioso romano. *Mundus, templum, urbs, ager, Latium, Italia* (pp. 440-553). Walter De Gruyter.
- Catalano, P. (1978). Aspetti spaziali del sistema giuridico-religioso romano. *Mundus, templum, urbs, ager, Latium, Italia*, in ANRW, *Principat, II, 16, 1*, a cura di H. Temporini e W. Haase, Berlin-New York, pp. 442-553.
- De Beer, S. (2004). *The Panegyric Inventio: A Rhetorical Analysis of Panegyricus Latinus V. In The Manipulative Mode* (pp. 295-318). Brill.
- Eckstein, A. M. (1979). The Foundation Day of Roman "Coloniae". *California Studies in Classical Antiquity*, 12, 8.
- Espinosa, D. E., González-García, A. C., & Quintela, M. V. G. (2016). On the orientation of two Roman towns in the Rhine area. *Mediterranean Archaeology and Archaeometry*, 16(4), 233-240
- Goethert, K. P. (2003). Untersuchungen zum Gründungsschema des Stadtplanes der Colonia Augusta Treverorum: Die Geburt der Stadt an der Mosel. *Archäologisches Korrespondenzblatt*, 33(2), 239-258.
- Kleiner, D. E. E. (2014). *Roman Architecture. A Visual Guide*. Yale University Press. ISBN:9780300208016, 0300208014
- Linderski, J. (1983). *Natalis Patavii*. *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik*. Bd. 50 (1983), pp. 227-232.
- Marconi, G. (2013). La figura di Costantino nell'Ordo Panegyricorum. I panegiristi e la nascita del potere costantiniano. In *Enciclopedia costantiniana sulla figura e l'immagine dell'imperatore del cosiddetto 'Editto di Milano'* 313.
- Nissen, H. (1869). *Das templum: antiquarische untersuchungen*. Weidmann.
- Nixon, C. E. V. (1980). The Occasion and Date of Panegyric VIII (V), and the Celebration of Constantine's Quinquennialia. *Antichthon*, 14, 157-169.
- Sparavigna, A. C. (2021). Alexandria of Egypt and the Archaeoastronomy. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. Available <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3138100> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3138100>
- Sparavigna, A. C. (2020). Invito alla lettura dell'articolo intitolato "Il giorno di fondazione delle colonie romane" di Arthur Eckstein. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4106546>
- Sparavigna, A. C. (2022). Augusta Taurinorum, la fondazione della colonia e l'archeoastronomia di Heinrich Nissen. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6889952>

Sparavigna, A. C. (2022). Aosta, la geometria e i venti di Vitruvio. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5878364>

Sparavigna, A. C. (2024). Nissen, Nietzsche, Valetton, Castagnoli, Catalano, Le Gall ed altri ancora, e la loro opinione circa il templum e la direzione dei decumani delle città romane [Nissen, Nietzsche, Valetton, Castagnoli, Catalano, Le Gall and others, and their opinion about the templum and the direction of decumani of Roman towns] (January 19, 2024). Available at SSRN:

<https://ssrn.com/abstract=4700361> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4700361>

Sparavigna, A. C. (2024). The Town and the Templum, in the Discussions by Nissen, Nietzsche, Valetton, Catalano and many others. *International Journal of Sciences*, 13(01), 15-45.

Thulin, C. O. (1906). *Die etruskische disciplin..* (Vol. 2). W. Zachrissons boktryckeri a.-b..

Valetton, I. M. J. (1898). *De templis Romanis*. *Mnemosyne*, 1-93.

Valetton, I. M. J. (1892). *De templis romanis*. *Mnemosyne*, 338-390.

Valetton, I. M. J. (1893). *De Templis Romanis* (Continuantur ex Vol. XX pag. 390). *Mnemosyne*, EJ Brill.

Wilson, R.J.A. (2012). *Simitthus*. In *The Oxford Classical Dictionary*, Editors Spawforth, A., Eidinow, E., Hornblower, S. ISBN: 9780199545568, 0199545561